

Recycling fishery waste into biobased fertilizers: Agronomic performance and soil health impacts

Jingsi Zhang^{a,1} , Birgit Koll^c,
Ireene Roman^c, Merili Toom^b, Marta Aranguren^d, Susana Virgel Mentxaka^d, Annelly Kuu^e ,
Stefaan De Neve^f, Erik Meers^a

^a Laboratory for BioResource Recovery (Re-Source), Department of Green Chemistry and Technology, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University, Coupure Links 653, Ghent 9000, Belgium

^b Unit of Agrotechnology, Centre of Estonian Rural Research and Knowledge, J. Aamisepa 1, Jõgeva 48309, Estonia

^c Department of Plant Breeding, Centre of Estonian Rural Research and Knowledge, J. Aamisepa 1, Jõgeva 48309, Estonia

^d NEIKER, Basque Institute for Agricultural Research and Development, Basque Research and Technology Alliance, Parque Científico y Tecnológico de Bizkaia, P812, Derio E-48160, Spain

^e Institute of Agricultural and Environmental Sciences, Estonian University of Life Sciences, Friedrich Reinhold Kreutzwaldi 1a, Tartu 51014, Estonia

^f Research group Soil Fertility and Nutrient Management, Department of Environment, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University, Coupure Links 653, Ghent 9000, Belgium

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the agronomic performance and soil impact of biobased fertilizers derived from fishery waste and by-products as circular alternatives to synthetic nitrogen (N) fertilizers in short-term field experiments with broccoli. Four biobased fertilizers — bokashi pellet (BP), nutrient solution with amino acids (NPKA), fish sludge pellet (FSP), and protein fraction (PF) — were obtained from pilot installations across Europe. The evaluation focused on soil mineral N (SMN) dynamics, N use efficiency (NUE), crop yield, and soil biological responses. One week after transplanting and fertilization, SMN levels in the topsoil (0–10 cm) were the highest in the NPKA ($253 \pm 94 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) and PF ($181 \pm 45 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) treatments, comparable to the mineral fertilizer (MF; $237 \pm 5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$). In contrast, FSP ($68 \pm 17 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) and BP ($30 \pm 11 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) did not significantly differ from the unfertilized soil ($40 \pm 5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$). Early SMN availability showed a strong positive correlation with broccoli yield and N uptake. Crop yields ranged from 8594 to 14,842 kg ha^{-1} among the organic treatments, with NPKA and PF performing comparably to MF (14,726 kg ha^{-1}) and substantially better than FSP and BP. The control treatment (CON) yielded 9252 kg ha^{-1} . NPKA and PF also demonstrated the highest NUE values (108 % and 84.8 %, respectively), with estimated mineral fertilizer equivalents of 79.5 % and 62.7 %. Soil biological activity showed treatment-specific responses. Dehydrogenase activity, microbial biomass carbon, and phospholipid fatty acid profiles in the 0–10 cm soil layer were significantly affected by fertilizer treatments, though most microbial indicators returned to baseline levels post-harvest. Soil fauna responses were variable: Springtail abundance declined under MF, whereas mite populations were more sensitive to organic treatments. Overall, the findings suggest that certain biobased fertilizers, particularly NPKA and PF, can effectively replace mineral N fertilizers, maintaining crop productivity while enhancing soil health indicators. These results support the integration of fish waste-based biobased fertilizers into sustainable agricultural practices.

Abbreviations: NUE, nitrogen use efficiency; SMN, soil mineral nitrogen; CON, unfertilized control treatment; BP, bokashi pellet; NPKA, NPK solution with amino acids; FSP, fish sludge pellet; PF, protein fraction; MF, mineral fertilizer; $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, ammonium nitrogen; $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, nitrate nitrogen; MFE, mineral fertilizer equivalent.

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: liina.edesi@metk.agri.ee (L. Edesi), cagri.akyol@ugent.be (Ç. Akyol).

¹ Jingsi Zhang and Liina Edesi contributed equally to the paper.

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1. Introduction

The production of mineral fertilizers, which relies heavily on fossil fuels and non-renewable ore deposits, is highly energy-intensive and contributes significantly to environmental degradation, including the eutrophication of aquatic ecosystems (Zhang et al., 2023). Prolonged dependence on synthetic fertilizers has led to adverse soil impacts such as nutrient imbalances, degradation of soil structure, diminished microbial activity, and reductions in soil organic matter (Shrivastava et al., 2023). In response to these challenges, the European Union's Farm to Fork Strategy outlines key objectives for transitioning to more sustainable food systems. These include reducing nutrient losses by at least 50 % and decreasing overall fertilizer use by 20 % by 2030, while promoting environmentally responsible practices across agriculture, fishery, aquaculture, and the entire food value chain (EC, 2020).

The new Fertilizing Products Regulation (EU) 2019/1009, adopted on June 5, 2019 and enforced from July 16, 2022, establishes safety, quality and labelling standards for a broad range of alternative fertilizing products, facilitating their free movement in the EU market. Among these alternatives, biobased fertilizers have shown considerable potential to fully or partially substitute synthetic mineral fertilizers by adequately supplying nutrients to crops and improving crop yields (He et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2016). Their application - particularly products such as protein hydrolysates, composts, fermented materials, and digestates - has been associated with the preservation of soil quality and enhancement of soil organic matter. These amendments contribute to the stimulation of soil biota, maintenance of microbial and enzymatic activities, stabilization of soil functions, and improvement in both crop productivity and nutritional quality (Cao et al., 2011; Tatti et al., 2013; Zhao et al., 2016). For example, He et al. (2022) demonstrated that replacing mineral fertilizers with commercial organic fertilizers (Nitrogen (N): 1.78 %; organic matter (OM): 48.5 %) in wheat cultivation improved nutrient use efficiency and soil quality. Similarly, in paddy field trials, partial substitution of mineral fertilizers with compost granules led to increased nutrient availability and enhanced yields of winter wheat and summer rice (Zhao et al., 2016). Furthermore, the organic N in biobased fertilizers is less susceptible to leaching and volatilization than mineral N sources, offering an environmental advantage (Luo et al., 2023).

Soil health or soil quality reflects the sustainability of crop production, the ability of soil to support ecosystem functions; and its capacity to maintain environmental quality (He et al., 2022). To comprehensively assess the effects of organic fertilizer on soil quality, it is essential to evaluate not only physical and chemical parameters, such as soil organic matter, pH and nutrient levels, but also microbial and biological indicators (Arboláez et al., 2023). Organic fertilizers enhance soil quality and increase nutrient availability for plants while also fostering microbial biomass. This microbial biomass provides more food sources for soil fauna, which occupy multiple trophic levels within the soil food web. These organisms facilitate the fragmentation and decomposition of organic matter, further contributing to nutrient release (Betancur-Corredor et al., 2023; Cao et al., 2011). Based on two global meta-analyses, organic fertilization significantly increased microbial abundance and the density of soil fauna, such as springtails and mites, compared to mineral fertilization (Betancur-Corredor et al., 2023; Morugán-Coronado et al., 2022). While the microbial abundance was unaffected by the duration of the studies, the density of mite and springtails varied with experiment length, indicating that even short-term organic fertilization can influence microbial and biological responses.

Biobased fertilizers are derived from organic waste materials such as food scraps, manure, and crop residues, utilizing nutrient recovery processes to reclaim essential elements like N and phosphorus (P) for agricultural use. Among these, fishery waste—including fish processing waste and fish sludge—shows great potential for nutrient recovery. Zhang et al. (2023) summarized that approximately 10–30 % of the

protein remains in fish processing waste, like fish viscera, head, skin and frames. In 2018, about 27,000 tons of N were discharged from 1.35 million tons of fish farming in Norway, even though its aquaculture production accounted for only 1.65 % of the global output.

Nutrient-rich fertilizing products derived from fishery waste are promising alternatives to mineral fertilizers and have been used in various cases. García-Santiago et al. (2021) observed 4 % increase in total yield and 21 % increase in the number of number of grape tomato fruits when using fish protein hydrolysate applied via irrigation. In a field experiment, a plot fertilized with 65 t ha⁻¹ fish waste-based compost produced 30 % more potatoes compared to mineral fertilizer treatment (Illera-Vives et al., 2017). Similarly, aquaculture wastewater and fish sludge from aquaponics greenhouse enriched soil nutrient content, improved N use efficiency (NUE), promoted onion growth and N uptake, enhanced onion quality and increased soil microbial diversity (Fruscella et al., 2023). Despite the promising results, there is still insufficient information regarding the performance of fishery waste-derived fertilizing products under field conditions and their potential impacts on soil quality.

In this study, field trials were conducted to evaluate the agronomic, environmental and ecological performance of four different types of biobased fertilizers derived from fishery waste and/or by-products, in comparison to commercial mineral fertilizer. The evaluation was based on the following assessments: i) N mineralization and release dynamics, ii) NUE and crop yield, iii) soil health (measured through a set of soil bio-indicators), and iv) nitrate residues (to estimate the risk of N loss after harvest). We hypothesized that the application of fishery waste-derived fertilizers, produced using different sources and processing technologies, would contribute efficiently to crop growth and yield, enhance soil functionality and biodiversity by stimulating mesofauna activity, and reduce N losses via leaching, compared to the commercial mineral fertilizer.

The novelty of this research lies in its integrative, field-scale assessment of fishery waste-derived fertilizing products, incorporating diverse production technologies and raw material sources, —an area that has not yet been systematically studied in temperate agricultural soils. Unlike previous studies, which have primarily focused on greenhouse or small-scale applications, this study evaluates the comprehensive agro-environmental impacts—particularly on soil mesofauna biodiversity and N dynamics—under real field conditions. By linking soil biological indicators with NUE and environmental performance, this study provides a holistic understanding of how these alternative organic fertilizers influence soil functioning and sustainability. In doing so, it addresses key knowledge gaps in the transition toward circular and biobased nutrient management systems and helps to mitigate concerns associated with the use of animal waste and by-products in the production of biobased fertilizing products.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Field and climate description

The field experiment was carried out in Jõgeva, Estonia (58° 45' 47.22''N, 26° 24' 14.40''E; altitude 67 m above sea level), on a field that has been cultivated organically since 2010. The crop rotation of the field was as follows: 2017/2018 winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), 2019 various vegetables, 2020 potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.), 2021 barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.), 2021/2022 red clover (*Trifolium pratense* L.). Red clover was cut and ploughed into the soil as green manure in 2022. The soil at the field trial site is classified as Endogleyic Luvisol (WRB, 2014) with a silty loam texture, consisting of 16.6 % sand (2–0.060 mm), 70.0 % silt (0.060–0.002 mm) and 13.4 % clay (< 0.002 mm) (see Table 1).

The meteorological data were obtained from the field weather station located at Jõgeva. Climatically, Estonia belongs to the mixed-forest subregion of the Atlantic-continental region of the temperate zone,

Table 1

Physical-chemical characteristics (mean ± standard deviation; n = 3) of the field from 0–10 cm and 10–30 cm soil depths in Jõgeva, Estonia.

Characteristics	Units	0–10 cm	10–30 cm
pH-H ₂ O		6.15 ± 0.06	6.12 ± 0.07
Moisture	%	14.7 ± 0.63	17.9 ± 0.53
Organic matter	%	5.09 ± 0.26	5.09 ± 0.19
Total N	%	0.14 ± 0.002	0.13 ± 0.004
NH ₄ ⁺ -N	mg kg ⁻¹ DW	1.04 ± 0.05	2.02 ± 1.65
NO ₃ ⁻ -N	mg kg ⁻¹ DW	15.85 ± 4.33	16.0 ± 6.22
Total P	g kg ⁻¹	0.78 ± 0.10	0.82 ± 0.05
Mobile P	g kg ⁻¹	0.33 ± 0.008	0.32 ± 0.025
Total K	g kg ⁻¹	1.20 ± 0.03	1.33 ± 0.05

characterized by warm summers and moderately mild winters. The mean annual temperature is 4.7°C; with average temperatures of −6.6°C in February and + 16.3°C in July. Mean annual precipitation ranges from 500 to 700 mm (Raukas, 2018). During the experimental year, the vegetation period differed in terms of rainfall amount and distribution, as well as air temperature, as shown in Fig. 1. Transplanting of broccoli seedlings was postponed from the end of May to June 5, 2023, due to lingering night frosts. The average temperature during the first half of June was 15.3°C, but from June 14 onward, daily highs rose to 27–29°C. In July, the average temperature was 16.3°C, with daily highs between 19°C and 25°C. Despite the warm conditions, only 5.4 mm of precipitation fell between June 1 and June 20, necessitating two irrigations on June 20 and June 30 (10 L m⁻² total). The first significant rainfall occurred at the end of June, with 15.2 mm recorded, followed by substantial rainfall in July totaling 104.4 mm. As a result, the broccoli

matured quickly and was harvested on August 4, 2023.

2.2. Collection and characterization of biobased fertilizing products

The fertilizing products were collected from four pilot installations employing various nutrient recovery technologies on waste and by-products from fish and aquaculture industries. Briefly, bokashi pellet (BP) was produced via Bokashi fermentation using effective microorganisms, from shredded fish processing waste mixed with tree leaves, ash from oil shale-fired thermal power plant’s and food waste, with a production rate of approximately 200 kg/month. Fish sludge pellet (FSP) was obtained by drying fish sludge from aquaculture and supplied by a Norwegian company (confidential data). The protein fraction (PF) was generated from a 1:1 mixture of fish head and fish bones (dry basis) via twin-screw extrusion and enzymatic hydrolysis; and its production capacity is up to 200 kg/month. The NPK solution with amino acids (NPKA) was concentrated from membrane filtrates derived from fish viscera following acid autolysis with formic acid after grinding and oil separation. Approximately 120 L of NPKA can be produced per month at the pilot facility. The physical-chemical characteristics and nutrient contents of the fertilizing products are presented in Table 2.

To prevent N loss, fresh samples were used for total N analysis using the Kjeldahl digestion method. Ammonium N (NH₄⁺-N) and nitrate N (NO₃⁻-N) were extracted with 1 M potassium chloride solution and analyzed using a continuous auto-flow analyzer (Chemlab System 4, Skalar, the Netherlands) (Saju et al., 2022). Other macro- and micro-nutrients, as well as metals, were determined after microwave digestion (Ultra wave 1 and 2, Milestone Srl, Italy) using 65 % nitric acid at 215°C and 120 bar, followed by analysis with Inductively Coupled Plasma

Fig. 1. Temperatures and precipitation patterns during the 2023 growing season.

Table 2
Characteristics of fishery-waste derived fertilizing products (mean \pm standard deviation; n = 3; expressed in fresh mass).

Pilot location	Estonia	Norway	France	Spain
Biobased fertilizer	Bokashi pellet	Fish sludge pellet	Protein fraction	NPK solution with amino acid
Abbreviation	BP	FSP	PF	NPKA
pH _{H2O}	7.21 \pm 0.04	6.15 \pm 0.01	6.05 \pm 0.02	4.82 \pm 0.02
EC/(mS cm ⁻¹)	5.87 \pm 0.22	8.32 \pm 0.60	4.37 \pm 0.36	18.7 \pm 0.0
Dry matter/%	90.7 \pm 0.2	94.4 \pm 0.2	98.1 \pm 0.2	34.5 \pm 0.2
OM/% DM	61.9 \pm 1.3	82.5 \pm 0.4	83.8 \pm 0.7	78.8 \pm 0.2
TN/%	2.63 \pm 0.09	6.19 \pm 0.07	7.62 \pm 0.72	5.31 \pm 0.1
NH ₄ ⁺ -N/(g kg ⁻¹)	0.38 \pm 0.02	0.62 \pm 0.06	0.34 \pm 0.02	2.56 \pm 0.01
NO ₃ ⁻ -N/(g kg ⁻¹)	< 0.002	< 0.002	< 0.002	< 0.002
TC%	32.2 \pm 0.4	39.3 \pm 0.6	46.6 \pm 0.3	14.2 \pm 0.2
TOC/%	31.7	39.1	46.5	14.2
C/N	12.3:1	6.35:1	6.11:1	2.67:1
P/(g kg ⁻¹)	10.5 \pm 3.8	27.4 \pm 4.5	30.9 \pm 0.7	15.9 \pm 1.1
K/(g kg ⁻¹)	19.1 \pm 1.7	14.6 \pm 2.0	6.15 \pm 0.11	22.4 \pm 1.9

Optical Emission (ICP-OES; Thermo Fisher iCAP Q Scientific, USA). The volatile trace metal mercury (Hg) was analyzed using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). Plant available P was extracted using an ammonium lactate-acetic acid buffer and determined by ICP-OES (MEN 5793:2008). Dry matter (DM) content was calculated after oven-drying the samples at 105°C to a constant weight (ISO 18134-2:2017). Organic matter (OM) content was determined by calcining the samples at 550°C for 4 h (ISO 18122:2015). pH (pH_{H2O}) was measured with a pH-meter (Orion520A USA) following a 1/5 (w/v) water extraction after 16 h equilibration (ISO 2917:1999). Electrical conductivity (EC) was measured using a conductivity meter (WTW Tetra Con 96, Xylem Analytics, Weilheim in Oberbayern, Bavaria, Germany) from water extracts (ratio 1:5 w/v) after 1 h of shaking and filtration (EN 13038, 2011). All analyses were performed in triplicate.

2.3. Field trials

The field was ploughed in autumn 2022 and harrowed to a depth of 10 cm in spring 2023. Plot sizes were 1.4 \times 8 m (11.2 m²), with a spacing of 2.8 m between plots. The trial followed a randomized complete block design. The field trial with broccoli (*Brassica oleracea* L. convar. *botrytis* var. *italica* 'Cesar') was conducted between June and August, 2023. The trials included six treatments: (1) control (unfertilized, CON), (2) mineral fertilizer (MF), (3) solid biobased fertilizer BP, (4) solid biobased fertilizer FSP, (5) solid biobased fertilizer PF, and (6) liquid biobased fertilizer NPKA. Each treatment was replicated three times.

Fertilizers were applied prior to planting and incorporated shallowly into the soil. The liquid biobased fertilizer (NPKA) was diluted fivefold and applied to the plots with a watering can. The application rate for all fertilized treatments (2–6) was based on their N content, corresponding to a target fertilization rate of 120 kg N ha⁻¹ (see the e-supplementary file). In the MF treatment, N was provided in the form of NH₄⁺.

In each plot, 49 seedlings at the 4-leaf stage were planted at a spacing of 0.45 \times 0.45 m. Weed control was conducted manually, insect nets were used throughout the broccoli growing period. After harvest, winter wheat was sown in early September to utilize residual N and prevent nitrate leaching.

2.4. Plant analysis

Harvesting was carried out when the flower buds were compact and firm, 60 days after transplanting. The central 4 m section of each plot

(comprising 9 plants per plot) was harvested on August 4, 2023, for further analysis. Fresh aboveground biomass (heads, stalks and leaves) was weighed and then oven-dried at 60°C. The dried biomass was subsequently weighted again to determine dry matter content. Carbon (C) and N contents in the dried biomass were determined using elemental analysis via the DUMAS dry combustion method with a LECO 828 series analyzer (LECO Corporation, Michigan, USA).

2.5. Soil analysis

Soil samples were collected from the topsoil (0–10 cm) and subsurface layer (10–30 cm) of each replicated block. Sampling was conducted at multiple time points: two weeks before fertilization (T1) to establish a baseline, one week after fertilization (T2) to assess the initial soil nutrient status, and five days after broccoli harvest (T5) to evaluate the effects of fertilization and plant growth. Soil mineral N (SMN) levels were also measured in deeper soil layers (30–60 cm) across all treatments to assess N dynamics throughout the broccoli growing season (T1–T5). Additional soil samples were collected according to broccoli developmental stages (Meier, 1997): at T3 (BBCH 25, visible formation of the third side shoot), and T4 (BBCH 51, inflorescence branches beginning to elongate and readiness for harvest). Further samples were taken in November 2023 to monitor post-season nitrate residues. Fresh soil samples were transported in cool boxes immediately after collection and stored at 4°C prior to analysis.

Soil fauna (springtails and mites) were sampled using a 5 cm diameter soil corer to a depth of 0–20 cm. Four cores were collected from each plot, totalling 12 samples per treatment. Extraction was carried out using Tullgren funnels (Coleman et al., 2017), where soil samples were placed on a metal sieve under light to drive organisms into ethanol-filled collection vials. Samples were kept under light for 48 h. Specimens were then identified to species level using taxonomic keys by Fjellberg (1980), Fjellberg (1998) and Hopkin (2007).

Soil dehydrogenase activity (DHA) was determined following Tabatabai (1982). Soil samples (5 g) were incubated at 30°C for 24 h in the presence triphenyl-tetrazoliumchloride, an alternative electron acceptor. The resulting triphenyl formazan (TPF) was extracted with acetone and quantified spectrophotometrically at 546 nm (Bio-Photometer plus). Basal respiration (RCO₂) was measured by CO₂ evolution from fresh soil via titration in a static system (ISO 16072:2011). Samples were incubated for 24 h in closed vessels, released CO₂ was absorbed in 0.05 M sodium hydroxide solution (NaOH) and titrated with 0.1 M HCl to pH 8.3 in the presence of BaCl₂ (De Neve et al., 2003).

Microbial biomass carbon (MBC) was assessed using the chloroform fumigation-extraction method with 0.5 M K₂SO₄ (1:2 w/v ratio). Extracted total organic carbon (TOC) was quantified using a TOC analyzer (TOC-VCN, Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan). MBC was calculated from the TOC difference between fumigated and non-fumigated samples using a conversion factor of 0.45 (Joergensen and Mueller, 1996; Vance et al., 1987).

Microbial community composition was determined via phospholipid fatty acid (PLFA) extraction (Bligh and Dyer, 1959). PLFA is used as a viable bio-indicator to study microbial communities in soils. Approximately 4 g of freeze-dried soil was extracted following the method described by Börjesson et al. (1998). Phospholipids were separated using a solid-phase extraction column (Chromabond, Macherey-Nagel GmbH, Germany), methylated to produce fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES), and analyzed using a gas chromatograph/mass spectrometer (Agilent 7890 A/5975 C, USA). FAME identification was based on retention times using a C4–C24 bacterial FAME standard mix (Sigma-Aldrich), with methyl nonadecanoate (19:0) as an internal standard. Injections were performed in splitless mode at 250 °C, and separation was achieved on an Agilent HP-5MS capillary column (30 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.25 μ m) using helium as the carrier gas. FAMES were grouped to microbial type (Ameloot et al., 2015; Frostegård and Bååth, 1996): Gram-positive bacteria (i15:0, a15:0, i16:0, i17:0, a17:0), Gram-negative bacteria

(cy17:0, 16:1 ω 7, 18:1 ω 7, cy19:0), Actinobacteria (10Me16:0, 10Me17:0, 10Me18:0), and saprotrophic fungi (18:2 ω 6).

Total N, NH₄⁺-N and NO₃⁻-N, DM, OM, plant available P, and pH_{H2O} in soil were determined as described in Section 2.2. For multi-element analysis, oven-dried soil samples were sieved (2 mm), homogenized, and digested with aqua regia on a hot plate (Saju et al., 2022). Elemental concentrations were analyzed using ICP-OES.

2.6. Calculations

Nitrogen use efficiency (NUE%) is expressed by the percentage of the N used by plants from N-fertilized soil and was calculated as follow:

$$NUE(\%) = \frac{100 \times [N_{up} - N_{up}(X_0)]}{N_{applied}}$$

Where N_{up} is the N content in the aboveground biomass (kg N ha⁻¹) in the fertilized treatment, while $N_{up}(X_0)$ is the N content in aboveground biomass in unfertilized (CON) treatment (kg N ha⁻¹), $N_{applied}$ is the total N amount applied to other treatments (120 kg N ha⁻¹).

The bioavailability of N in biobased fertilizers was compared to mineral fertilizer (MF), where the availability of N is usually assumed to be 100 %. Mineral fertilizer equivalent (MFE%) of the biobased fertilizers was calculated as follow:

$$MFE(\%) = \frac{N_{up}(X) - N_{up}(X_0)}{N_{up}(X_{full}) - N_{up}(X_0)} \times 100$$

Where $N_{up}(X)$ is the N content in aboveground biomass fertilized with biobased fertilizers (N, kg ha⁻¹), $N_{up}(X_0)$ is the N content in the CON treatment's aboveground biomass (N, kg ha⁻¹), $N_{up}(X_{full})$ is the N content in the MF treatment's aboveground biomass (N, kg ha⁻¹).

2.7. Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were conducted using RStudio v1.3.1093 running R software v4.1.2 (R Core Team, 2020). Figures were generated using the ggplot2 package (Ginestet, 2011). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using the aov function from the stats package (R Core Team, 2020). Data normality was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test ($p < 0.01$), and homogeneity of variance was tested using Levene's test using Levene's test function from the car package (Fox and Weisberg, 2014). When significant treatment effects were observed, differences between means were evaluated using Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) test. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation (SD), were also reported.

Spearman rank correlation coefficients were calculated to assess relationships between variables. Significant correlations between soil chemical properties and microbial parameters were visualized using the PerformanceAnalytics package. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted to explore relationships among microbial community, DHA, and soil chemical properties.

The mean number and standard error (SE) of springtails individuals were calculated. Nonparametric statistical methods, including Spearman correlation, were used to assess soil fauna data, using STATISTICA 7 and Microsoft Excel. The Shannon-Wiener diversity index was calculated to assess species diversity (Krebs, 1999; Spellerberg, 2005). Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) was performed to investigate relationships between springtail communities and environmental variables using CANOCO 4.52 (Ter Braak, 1994). Forward selection with the Monte Carlo permutation test (999 permutations) to identify significant environmental variables affecting community composition.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characteristics of the fertilizing products

The four fertilizing products met the nutrient contents and pollutant limit requirements outlined in the Product Function Categories (PFCs) of Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 and can potentially be classified as organic fertilizer (PFC 1[A]). All solid fertilizers contained between 31.7 % and 46.5 % TOC (Table 2), exceeding the minimum required value of 15 %. The liquid NPKA fertilizer contained 14.2 % TOC, surpassing the 5 % threshold for liquid fertilizers. The solid fertilizers contained at least 2.5 % N, while the liquid fertilizer contained at least 2 % N. All tested pollutants, including cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), mercury (Hg), as well as micronutrients Zn and Cu, were within the permissible limits (see the e-supplementary file).

3.2. Nitrogen release dynamics and mineralization

The N supply from organic biobased fertilizer consisted of mineral N — in the forms of ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻) — and organic N, which might be either readily mineralizable over the short term (e.g., during the growing season) or recalcitrant and thus not immediately plant available. The initial NH₄⁺-N and NO₃⁻-N contents of the organic fertilizers were low (see Table 2), indicating that the N release in the amended soil was primarily due to the mineralization of the organic N they contained. N mineralization plays a crucial role in regulating the N availability in soil (Liu et al., 2022). Changes in SMN reflect the N mineralized from both soil organic matter and organic amendments.

The SMN levels during the field trial is shown in Fig. 2. The SMN content before the fertilization (T1) was 18 ± 2 kg ha⁻¹ at 0–10 cm depth, 35 ± 4 kg ha⁻¹ at 10–30 cm, and 49 ± 12 kg ha⁻¹ at 30–60 cm. Red clover (a legume) was used as green manure to fix atmospheric N for subsequent crops and was ploughed into the soil the previous autumn. According to McKenna et al. (2018), annual N fixation of red clover can range from 30 to 250 kg ha⁻¹, potentially supplying N to unfertilized soil. As a result of red clover degradation, SMN levels in the unfertilized CON treatment at 0–30 cm depth increased from 53 ± 19 kg ha⁻¹ to 93 ± 11 kg ha⁻¹ one week after fertilization (T2).

The C/N ratio of organic fertilizers plays an important role in N mineralization and immobilization processes in soils and is considered a useful indicator for soil fertility and management (Watson et al., 2002). In our previous studies, fertilizing products with higher readily available N — reflected in higher ratio of initial mineral N/Total N (TN), and lower C/N ratio — performed better in terms of nutrient supply and agronomic response (Luo et al., 2022; Sigurnjak et al., 2017). In this study, the initial mineral N contents of the biobased fertilizers were very low, and the N-release process was dominated by microbial mineralization of organic N. The liquid NPKA contained only 2.56 g kg⁻¹ MN, approximately 5 % of its TN, and had a lower C/N ratio (2.67:1) than the other three biobased fertilizers. It was the most effective in supplying plant available N, as reflected by the high SMN levels (253 ± 94 kg ha⁻¹) in the 0–10 cm layer of the soil one week after fertilization (T2) (see Fig. 2). In contrast, the solid BP, with a higher C/N ratio (12.3:1), resulted in the lowest SMN level (30 ± 11 kg ha⁻¹) in the 0–10 cm layer — even lower than the unfertilized CON (40 ± 5 kg ha⁻¹) — indicating net N immobilization in the amended soil. Previous studies suggest that when the C/N ratio of an organic amendment is below a threshold of 15:1 (or even up to 25:1), N is mineralized more rapidly and becomes available for direct crop uptake, depending on the type of organic amendment (Calderón et al., 2005; Gale et al., 2006; Lazicki et al., 2020; Myrold and Bottomley, 2008). However, the BP product had the lowest TN content and the highest C/N ratio (12.3:1) among the tested fertilizers. As a result, it was applied at a 2–3 times higher rate than the other fertilizers, leading to increased N immobilization in microbial biomass shortly after the fertilization (T2) and low SMN levels throughout the growing period.

Fig. 2. Soil mineral N (SMN, mean \pm standard deviation, kg ha⁻¹, n = 3) at different depths (0–10 cm, 10–30 cm, 30–60 cm) at four sampling times: T2 (one week after fertilization), T3 (at BBCH 25, visible formation of the 3rd side shoot), T4 (at BBCH 51 when the branches of inflorescence begin to elongate) and T5 (after harvest). The letters refer to the statistical difference (one-way ANOVA, Tukey HSD, $p < 0.05$) of SMN between treatments in the 0–10 cm and 10–30 cm soil layers, respectively. No significant difference was observed in SMN levels in the 30–60 cm soil layer. CON: control, unfertilized treatment; MF: mineral fertilizer; BP: bokashi pellet; FSP: fish sludge pellet; PF: protein fraction; NPKA: NPK solution with amino acids.

The types of waste streams and physical forms of organic fertilizers can also influence the N release dynamics. Treatments with pelletized products BP and FSP exhibited lower SMN levels compared to the loose solid fertilizer PF, and showed no significant differences from the unfertilized CON treatment during the first month of broccoli growth (by T3) (see Fig. 2). Recalcitrant organic matter, such as lignin, slows down net N mineralization and thus results in lower N release over a given period, whereas waste materials with higher protein content, such as slaughter food waste, tend to result in higher mineralized N levels (Lazicki et al., 2020; Myrold and Bottomley, 2008). Another contributing factor is that the fertilizer pelleting slows down nutrient release, reducing nutrient accessibility for soil microbes and crops during the early days of application (Monaci et al., 2022). Niedziński et al. (2021) reported that only 15–28 % of N was released from organic pellets derived from turkey manure and post-mushroom substrate after 35 days of incubation. In our study, weather conditions further hindered pellet decomposition, as there was no precipitation at the beginning of the growing season. Despite having similar C/N ratios (6.11 for PF and 6.37 for FSP), the loose solid product PF — derived purely from fish processing waste — and the pelletized FSP — made from dried fish sludge — showed different N release behaviours after application. By T2, the PF treatment had significantly higher mineral N levels (181 ± 45 kg ha⁻¹) in the 0–10 cm layer, approximately 1.5 times greater than those observed in the FSP treatment (68 ± 17 kg ha⁻¹).

Broccoli is a high-N demanding crop, and its uptake patterns significantly influences SMN levels. After transplanting, broccoli exhibits a typical growth trajectory: very slow initial biomass accumulation and N uptake, followed by rapid growth and nutrient demand in later stages (Shan et al., 2022; Smith et al., 2016; Vågen et al., 2007; Wyland et al., 1996). The SMN levels in the treatments reflect the

potential pool of plant available N generated through mineralization of organic N in both unfertilized and fertilized soil across different growth phases of broccoli. From T2 to T3 (four weeks after fertilization), SMN levels decreased markedly to 31, 35, 62 kg ha⁻¹ in the CON, BP and FSP treatment, respectively, and to 138, 212, 234 kg ha⁻¹ in the PF, NPKA and MF treatments, respectively, in the 0–60 cm soil layer. From T3 to T4 (eight weeks after fertilization), SMN levels further declined to 9, 11, 10 kg ha⁻¹ in the CON, BP and FSP, and to 15, 18, 11 kg ha⁻¹ in the PF, NPKA and MF, respectively, in the 0–60 cm soil layer.

Fertilizer treatments with slower mineralization rates (i.e., BP, FSP) contributed to more N during the later growth stages, while the liquid product NPKA — with the highest mineralization rate — supplied luxury N from the beginning. The PF treatment, in contrast, provided a relatively balanced supply of plant available N throughout the first and second half of the broccoli growth cycle. By T4, there were no longer significant differences in SMN levels among treatments. After harvest (from T4 to T5), a slight increase in SMN levels was observed in all treatments, with values ranging from 4 to 10 kg ha⁻¹ in the 0–10 cm layer and approximately 10–15 kg ha⁻¹ in the 10–30 cm layer, likely due to organic residue decomposition. In the 30–60 cm layer, no significant differences in SMN levels were observed among treatments at any sampling time. In fact, SMN levels during broccoli growth were often lower than those in the unfertilized soil at the beginning of the experiment (T1).

3.3. Agronomic performance of the fertilizing products

3.3.1. Crop yield

Yields, harvest index (HI), N concentrations, NUE%, and MFE% of broccoli under different treatments are presented in Table 3. Biomass

Table 3

Fresh and dry yields of broccoli head and total aboveground biomass (including heads, stalks and leaves), harvest index (HI), N concentrations in broccoli plants and yield, N use efficiency (NUE%) and N mineral fertilizer equivalence (MFE %) under different treatments (mean \pm SD, $n = 3$).

Treatment	Yield (heads)	Yield (aboveground part)	Yield (heads)	Yield (aboveground part)	HI	Total N	N uptake	NUE	MFE
	kg ha ⁻¹	kg ha ⁻¹	kg ha ⁻¹ DM	DM kg ha ⁻¹	%	%	kg ha ⁻¹	%	%
CON	9252 \pm 84	46,821 \pm 3,818d	909 \pm 71	6460 \pm 280c	14.1 \pm 1.7	2.35 \pm 0.31b	152 \pm 26d		
MF	14,726 \pm 6124	79,401 \pm 8,179a	1489 \pm 507	9390 \pm 1,430a	15.7 \pm 3.7	3.34 \pm 0.18a	315 \pm 57a	135 \pm 48a	
BP	8594 \pm 2496	50,915 \pm 4865 cd	830 \pm 183	6720 \pm 570bc	12.3 \pm 2.3	2.45 \pm 0.27b	165 \pm 27 cd	10.6 \pm 22.4c	7.87 \pm 16.53c
FSP	10,455 \pm 3013	56,749 \pm 7,277bcd	1142 \pm 348	7640 \pm 660abc	14.8 \pm 3.3	2.65 \pm 0.39ab	202 \pm 36bcd	41.7 \pm 29.8bc	30.9 \pm 22.0bc
PF	12,007 \pm 593	65,774 \pm 2,651abc	1332 \pm 176	8260 \pm 380abc	16.1 \pm 1.4	3.09 \pm 0.34ab	254 \pm 17abc	84.8 \pm 14.1abc	62.7 \pm 10.4abc
NPKA	14,843 \pm 2086	68,240 \pm 4,568ab	1383 \pm 141	8540 \pm 330ab	16.2 \pm 1.8	3.30 \pm 0.24a	281 \pm 17ab	108 \pm 14ab	79.5 \pm 10.2ab
<i>F value</i>	2.271	14.21	2.753	7.162	1.057	6.500	11.81	9.31	9171
<i>Pr(>F)</i>	n.s.	< 0.001	n.s.	0.0025	n.s.	0.0038	< 0.001	0.0021	0.0022

Unfertilized (CON), mineral fertilizers (MF) and biobased fertilizers; bokashi pellet (BP), fish sludge pellet (FSP), protein fraction (PF) and NPK solution with amino acids (NPKA). Different letters indicate significant differences between treatments at $p < 0.05$ with Tukey-Kramer (HSD) test.

n.s.: not significant

yield, both fresh and dry, was significantly influenced by the treatment ($p \leq 0.001$; $p = 0.0025$, respectively), while no significant differences were observed in head yields, which ranged from 8594 to 14,842 kg ha⁻¹ among treatments. Broccoli growth is highly affected by environmental conditions, with climate being a key factor (Siomos et al., 2022). Mediterranean countries — particularly Italy and Spain — are the two leading European producers of broccoli and cauliflower. In the same climatic zone with Estonia, the neighbouring countries Latvia and Lithuania recorded average yields of only 8013 kg ha⁻¹ and 5791 kg ha⁻¹ kg ha⁻¹, respectively, for broccoli and cauliflower in recent years, while Estonia, despite having the lowest production overall, achieved a mean yield of 10,120 kg ha⁻¹ between 2004 and 2018 (FAOSTAT, 2022).

In our study, the highest aboveground biomass yield was recorded in the MF treatment (79,401 kg ha⁻¹), followed by the biobased fertilizer treatments PF and NPKA (65,774 kg ha⁻¹ and 68,240 kg ha⁻¹, respectively). Significantly lower biomass yield was observed in the unfertilized CON treatment and the BP treatment (46,821 kg ha⁻¹ and 50,915 kg ha⁻¹, respectively). These results suggest that the BP treatment did not release N rapidly enough to meet the growth demands of broccoli, consistent with its known N release and mineralization patterns. The PF and NPKA treatments performed comparably to the MF treatment in supplying plant available N and supporting crop yields.

The optimal fertilization rate for maximum yield varies widely under different conditions, ranging from 112 to 450 kg N ha⁻¹ (Conversa et al., 2019). Despite applying only 120 kg N ha⁻¹, we achieved a substantial biomass yield. This is most likely due to N supplied by the ploughed-in red clover, which contributed significantly to meeting the crop's N demand. This is supported by the high SMN of 112 \pm 36 kg ha⁻¹ in the 0–60 cm soil layer, already present at T1. According to Viil and Vösa (2005), as much as 160 kg ha⁻¹ of N can remain in the soil during the year of red clover sowing alone. In our study, the native soil was able to supply 152 kg N ha⁻¹ for broccoli growth, based on the N uptake of the aboveground biomass in the unfertilized CON treatment. In addition to the N applied through fertilization, the crop also benefited from SMN derived from the green manure crop, which contributed to increased production.

The dry head yield was significantly correlated with SMN levels (0–60 cm) at T2 ($r = 0.773$, $p < 0.001$) and T3 ($r = 0.528$, $p < 0.05$) (see the e-supplementary file). Notably, even stronger correlations were observed between the crop yield and early SMN levels (0–60 cm) at T2 ($r = 0.836$, $p < 0.001$) and T3 ($r = 0.738$, $p < 0.001$). Treatments with fertilizers MF, NPKA and PF produced significantly higher fresh

aboveground biomass compared to the CON treatment, consistent with their N release profiles in elevated SMN levels during early growth stages. These results confirm that broccoli is strongly influenced by N availability during the early growth period.

Similarly, Vågen et al. (2007) reported that the yield of broccoli heads from the same cultivar increased almost linearly with SMN level (0–30 cm) up to approximately 230 kg N ha⁻¹. In our study, SMN levels in both the 0–60 cm or 0–30 cm were strongly correlated with the dry yields of both the entire plant and head. The head yields of the different treatments followed the same trends as total aboveground biomass — namely, MF > NPKA > PF > FSP > CON > BP — although no statistically differences were observed among treatments in head yield.

The harvest index (HI) represents the fraction of the harvested broccoli head relative to the total aboveground biomass on a dry weight basis. In our study, the NPKA and PF treatments had higher HI values than the MF treatment, while the BP treatment had the lowest head yield and HI. This was likely due to the limited N availability early in the growing period, resulting from N immobilization (Fig. 2). Vågen et al. (2007) reported that broccoli head yield was more closely related to crop N uptake than total biomass yield; with head yield decreasing sharply under low N supply. Conversa et al. (2019) found that the broccoli HI remained stable when N uptake ranged between 170 and 200 kg ha⁻¹. Vågen et al. (2007) also observed that, under climate conditions similar to Estonia (in southernmost Norway), broccoli grown in silty showed increased head yield and HI as N fertilization rates increased from 0 to 240 kg N ha⁻¹. Specifically, the HI rose from 0.17 in the unfertilized control and to 0.23 at 120 kg N ha⁻¹. In comparison, our study recorded lower head yield and HI values, which might be attributed to the use of different broccoli cultivars and a lower plant density of 43,750 plants ha⁻¹, compared to of 57,000 plants ha⁻¹ in the referenced study.

Many factors beyond fertilization influence the growth, development, and yield of broccoli, including soil moisture, temperature, and cultivar type (Conversa et al., 2019; Shan et al., 2022; Siomos et al., 2022; Vågen et al., 2007). Studies reported that different cultivars respond variably to N availability and biomass yield, and exhibit differing sensitivity to heat stress. Broccoli generally thrives within a temperature range of 5–25 °C, with the optimal range for growth typically between 15 and 23 °C, depending on the genotype (Siomos et al., 2022). Most broccoli cultivars initiate head development most rapidly at temperatures between 15 and 20 °C (Cammarano et al., 2020).

Kalużewicz et al. (2009) found that during the vegetative growth phase, head yield was highest at temperature between 15 and 25 °C;

however, prolonged exposure to temperatures above 20°C during the harvest period led to reduced head yields. In our study, daily high temperatures exceeding 20°C in the late growth stage may have contributed to earlier harvesting (60 days after transplanting) than expected, as the vegetative phase for the cultivated variety lasts 80–90 days. This premature harvest likely affected head yield and resulted in lower HI.

3.3.2. Nitrogen use efficiency

The total N content of the harvested broccoli varied significantly among the treatments ($p = 0.0038$). The MF treatment resulted in the highest crop N content (3.34 %), followed by the biobased fertilizer treatments NPKA (3.30 %) and PF (3.09 %). In contrast, the CON (2.35 %), BP (2.45 %), and FSP (2.65 %) treatments showed relatively lower total N content in the broccoli. Crop N uptake also differed significantly across treatments ($p < 0.001$). The highest N uptake was observed in the MF treatment (314 kg ha⁻¹), followed by NPKA (281 kg ha⁻¹) and PF (254 kg ha⁻¹). The lowest uptake was recorded in the CON (152 kg ha⁻¹), BP (165 kg ha⁻¹), and FSP (202 kg ha⁻¹) treatments.

N uptake was strongly correlated with early-stage SMN levels (0–60 cm), both at T2 ($r = 0.902$, $p < 0.001$) and T3 ($r = 0.807$, $p < 0.001$) (see the e-supplementary file). These results indicate that higher N availability during the early stages of crop development tended to result in greater total N uptake by the plants (Luo et al., 2022). This also suggests that the early-season SMN levels may serve as a reliable predictor of broccoli N uptake during later growth stages.

In terms of the N uptake by broccoli plants, it is notable that the pre-cultivation of red clover contributed approximately 152 kg N ha⁻¹, as reflected by the N uptake in the unfertilized CON treatment. When accounting for fertilization, total N availability in the fertilized soils was estimated at around 272 kg N ha⁻¹. Although previous studies have reported optimal N fertilization rates for broccoli ranging from 112 to 450 kg N ha⁻¹, Vågen et al., (2007) demonstrated that a rate as low as 120 kg N ha⁻¹ could produce approximately 14,440 kg ha⁻¹ of fresh broccoli heads with a N recovery rate of 82 %. This yield is comparable to the mean yield of 13,472 kg ha⁻¹ for broccoli and cauliflower in recent years in Norway (FAOSTAT, 2022).

In our study, higher N uptake than 272 kg N ha⁻¹ was observed in the MF and NPKA treatments. This may be attributed to priming effects, where fertilizer addition stimulates the mineralization of the native soil organic N, thereby increasing the pool of plant available N (Luo et al., 2023; Monaci et al., 2022; Sigurnjak et al., 2017). This interpretation is supported by the NUE% results, which showed that plants in the MF, NPKA, and PF treatments assimilated significantly ($p = 0.0021$) more N than was directly supplied by the fertilizers. In contrast, significantly lower NUE was observed in the BP and FSP treatments, with NUE% values of 10.6 % and 41.7 %, respectively, due to the limited N availability in soil during the growth period of broccoli.

The MFE, indicating the effectiveness of biobased fertilizer relative to mineral fertilizer, also varied significantly among treatments ($p = 0.0022$). The NPKA and PF products showed higher MFE values (79.5 % and 62.7 %, respectively), suggesting their strong potential as alternatives to synthetic fertilizers. In contrast, BP and FSP had substantially lower MFE values (7.87 % and 30.9 %, respectively), reflecting their lower efficiency in N utilization over the two-month broccoli growing period.

The biobased fertilizers NPKA and PF demonstrated strong potential to enhance both broccoli yield and NUE. These treatments outperformed others in terms of N release and crop productivity, particularly when N availability was well aligned with the plant's early growth demands. Elevated early-stage SMN levels, — likely supported by the incorporation of red clover as green manure — played a critical role in these outcomes. The strong correlation between early N availability and increased biomass yield underscores the importance of synchronizing nutrient supply with early crop development stages.

The HI was notably higher in the NPKA and PF treatments, underscoring their effectiveness in promoting optimal crop development. These biobased fertilizers also exhibited higher MFE, indicating a more efficient N utilization compared to the treatments such as BP and FSP. In contrast, the BP treatment showed lower performance, likely due to N immobilization and inadequate early-stage N availability.

Overall, these findings support the potential role of biobased fertilizers — particularly when their N release is well synchronized with crop demand — to enhance productivity. Furthermore, the incorporation of green manure-derived N, especially from red clover, significantly contributed to total N uptake and supports the integration of sustainable fertilization practices in vegetable cropping systems.

3.4. Effects of the fertilizing products on soil physical-chemical and biological characteristics

3.4.1. Soil physicochemical characteristics

The application of organic-rich biobased fertilizers increased soil OM content; however, no significant differences were observed between treatments at either T2 or T5 (see the e-supplementary file). This lack of differentiation may be attributed to the addition of N, which decreased the soil C/N ratio, meeting microbial requirements and thereby enhancing the decomposition of added OM. Tuomisto et al. (2012) conducted a meta-analysis of 56 European cases and found that organic farming generally leads to higher soil OM contents, with median increase of 7 % compared to conventional farming. However, their meta-analysis also revealed that OM inputs alone cannot fully explain the changes in soil OM, other factors such as crop residues, duration of organic management, and agricultural history should be considered. Similarly, Betancur-Corredor et al. (2023) found that organic fertilizers do not significantly affect soil OM and pH. In our study, soil pH values varied only slightly, with the BP treatment showing a higher pH (see the e-supplementary file), likely due to both the inherently higher pH of the BP product and the larger quantity applied.

No significant differences in total P were found in the 0–10 cm soil layer; however, significant differences in plant-available P were observed between treatments in this same depth by T2. The MF treatment showed significantly higher potassium (K) content than the unfertilized CON in the 0–10 cm soil layer by T2. However, no significant differences in plant-available P and K were detected between treatments after harvesting. Calcium (Ca) content showed no significant variation throughout the cultivation period, while sodium (Na) content varied slightly, ranging from 0.05–0.07 g kg⁻¹ DW. The MF treatment exhibited comparatively higher levels of Ca and sulphur (S) in the shallow 0–10 cm soil layer. Similarly, no significant differences in these nutrients were observed between treatments after harvesting.

3.4.2. Microbial activities

DHA, MBC, RCO₂, and microbial community composition are key indicators soil microbial activity and functionality. DHA reflects the ability of soil microorganisms to catalyse redox reactions (Dick, 1997; Gu et al., 2009). In this study, significant differences in microbial indicators primarily were observed in the upper 0–10 cm soil layer, where fertilizers were incorporated. One week after fertilization (T2), treatments showed significant differences in the DHA levels at 0–10 cm soil layer ($p < 0.001$), ranging from 4.01 to 10.33 TPF, µg g⁻¹ h⁻¹ (see Table 4). After harvest (T5), most differences in microbial parameters had diminished, with the exception of DHA, which remained significantly different among treatments in the 0–10 cm soil layer ($p = 0.0032$). At both T2 and T5, the BP treatment exhibited the highest DHA (10.33 and 7.37 TPF, µg g⁻¹ h⁻¹ respectively), indicating elevated microbial metabolic activity. In contrast, the MF treatment showed the lowest DHA (4.01 and 4.72 TPF, µg g⁻¹ h⁻¹ respectively).

The higher DHA in the BP treatment might be attributed to its significantly greater application rate (4563 kg ha⁻¹), which resulted in an additional carbon input of 565.7–1245.6 kg TC ha⁻¹ compared to the

Table 4

Dehydrogenase activity (DHA), microbial biomass carbon (MBC), basal respiration (RCO₂), and phospholipid fatty acid (PLFA) concentrations (nmol g⁻¹) in 0–10 and 10–30 cm soil layers at three sampling times: T1 (before fertilization), T2 (one week after fertilization), and T5 (after harvest), under different fertilizer treatments (mean ± SD, n = 3).

Sampling time	Treatment	Depth cm	DHA	MBC	RCO ₂	Actinobacteria	G ⁺	G ⁻	Saprotrophic fungi
			TPF (μg g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	ug C g ⁻¹ soil DM	μg CO ₂ g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹	nmol g ⁻¹	nmol g ⁻¹	nmol g ⁻¹	nmol g ⁻¹
T1	OS	0–10	3.58 ± 0.80	181 ± 24	2.07 ± 0.45	2.93 ± 0.43	8.83 ± 1.3	4.14 ± 0.64	0.19 ± 0.06
	OS	10–30	4.19 ± 0.52	231 ± 25	3.23 ± 0.70	3.18 ± 0.09	10.0 ± 0.3	4.96 ± 0.05	0.48 ± 0.13
T2	CON	0–10	4.20 ± 0.50c	112 ± 8b	3.29 ± 2.70	3.19 ± 0.06a	10.1 ± 0.6b	4.26 ± 0.13abc	0.20 ± 0.03b
	MF	0–10	4.01 ± 0.39c	60 ± 10b	4.68 ± 3.56	2.95 ± 0.03a	8.88 ± 0.53b	3.84 ± 0.17c	0.24 ± 0.01b
	BP	0–10	10.3 ± 2.3a	207 ± 50ab	5.64 ± 0.40	3.18 ± 0.06a	10.4 ± 0.4b	5.06 ± 0.69ab	0.70 ± 0.28ab
	FSP	0–10	5.72 ± 0.51bc	109 ± 11ab	4.97 ± 2.50	2.95 ± 0.20a	9.14 ± 0.77b	4.21 ± 0.45bc	0.38 ± 0.12b
	PF	0–10	7.59 ± 1.63ab	340 ± 130a	5.06 ± 0.02	3.34 ± 0.31a	10.1 ± 0.7b	5.06 ± 0.31ab	1.10 ± 0.28a
	NPKA	0–10	7.59 ± 0.10ab	187 ± 66ab	4.60 ± 2.33	3.19 ± 0.27a	14.5 ± 2.0a	5.29 ± 0.19a	1.10 ± 0.42a
	CON	10–30	4.89 ± 0.43a	114 ± 19a	2.74 ± 0.77	2.99 ± 0.21a	8.86 ± 0.4b	4.09 ± 0.28a	0.24 ± 0.02b
	MF	10–30	4.33 ± 0.49a	93 ± 30a	5.06 ± 1.04	3.10 ± 0.05a	9.63 ± 0.48ab	4.44 ± 0.26a	0.27 ± 0.05ab
	BP	10–30	6.12 ± 1.3a	101 ± 21a	4.93 ± 2.58	3.07 ± 0.29a	9.48 ± 1.0ab	4.42 ± 0.49a	0.45 ± 0.21ab
	FSP	10–30	5.18 ± 0.64a	113 ± 28a	9.03 ± 5.51	3.16 ± 0.23a	9.58 ± 1.20ab	4.33 ± 0.64a	0.34 ± 0.09ab
	PF	10–30	6.49 ± 0.58a	146 ± 56a	5.78 ± 3.14	3.37 ± 0.11a	10.3 ± 0.1ab	5.08 ± 0.44a	0.54 ± 0.07a
	NPKA	10–30	4.69 ± 0.95a	119 ± 25a	2.31 ± 1.25	3.20 ± 0.21a	11.0 ± 0.5a	4.68 ± 0.20a	0.35 ± 0.06ab
T5	CON	0–10	4.72 ± 0.15b	157 ± 14a	1.90 ± 0.02	3.09 ± 0.43a	9.01 ± 1.1a	3.78 ± 0.37a	0.25 ± 0.06a
	MF	0–10	4.72 ± 0.43b	157 ± 18a	2.18 ± 2.75	4.21 ± 1.28a	12.1 ± 4.3a	5.33 ± 1.68a	0.52 ± 0.18a
	BP	0–10	7.37 ± 0.63a	212 ± 33a	1.46 ± 0.83	3.21 ± 0.08a	9.59 ± 0.35a	4.57 ± 0.26a	0.56 ± 0.13a
	FSP	0–10	6.17 ± 0.90ab	209 ± 73a	2.51 ± 0.64	3.43 ± 0.15a	10.5 ± 0.7a	4.56 ± 0.31a	0.51 ± 0.16a
	PF	0–10	6.70 ± 1.22a	199 ± 4a	5.67 ± 6.11	3.82 ± 0.14a	10.7 ± 0.2a	4.98 ± 0.51a	0.55 ± 0.28a
	NPKA	0–10	5.86 ± 0.32ab	177 ± 32a	2.84 ± 0.04	4.19 ± 1.27a	12.9 ± 3.9a	5.25 ± 1.42a	0.41 ± 0.14a
	CON	10–30	4.39 ± 0.69a	151 ± 10a	2.27 ± 2.16	3.40 ± 1.00a	10.3 ± 2.9a	4.26 ± 1.10a	0.30 ± 0.11a
	MF	10–30	4.50 ± 0.29a	161 ± 29a	0.34 ± 0.15	3.59 ± 0.79a	11.0 ± 3.2a	4.41 ± 0.71a	0.24 ± 0.08a
	BP	10–30	5.35 ± 0.95a	212 ± 89a	1.57 ± 0.54	3.19 ± 0.30a	9.87 ± 1.37a	4.28 ± 0.48a	0.34 ± 0.08a
	FSP	10–30	4.38 ± 0.55a	182 ± 11a	9.47 ± 7.97	3.16 ± 0.09a	9.57 ± 0.4a	3.93 ± 0.19a	0.33 ± 0.06a
	PF	10–30	5.11 ± 0.46a	174 ± 19a	4.35 ± 2.03	3.56 ± 0.69a	10.8 ± 2.2a	4.49 ± 1.13a	0.33 ± 0.15a
	NPKA	10–30	5.31 ± 0.86a	174 ± 23a	2.99 ± 0.34	3.22 ± 0.33a	9.9 ± 1.3a	4.12 ± 0.59a	0.31 ± 0.08a

Unfertilized (CON), mineral fertilizers (MF) and biobased fertilizers; bokashi pellet (BP), fish sludge pellet (FSP), protein fraction (PF) and NPK solution with amino acids (NPKA). Different letters indicate significant differences between treatments at $p < 0.05$ with Tukey-Kramer (HSD) test.

other biobased treatments. Previous researches have also demonstrated that organic fertilizer use can enhance microbial diversity and activity by enriching the soil's carbon pool (Peacock et al., 2001; Wu et al., 2008; Dijkstra et al., 2009).

MBC is primarily influenced by soil organic carbon, pH and management practices, and is commonly used as an early indicator to reflect changes mainly induced by abiotic stress (Amahnui et al., 2023; Anderson and Domsch, 1989; Kallenbach and Grandy, 2011; Yu et al., 2020). At the T2 sampling time (0–10 cm depth), the PF treatment exhibited the highest MBC level at 339.74 μg C g⁻¹ soil DM ($p = 0.0022$), followed by the BP treatment at 207.34 μg C g⁻¹ soil DM. In contrast, the MF treatment showed the lowest MBC level at 59.77 μg C g⁻¹ soil DM.

RCO₂ reflects the oxidative capacity of soil microorganisms and is influenced by both energy sources and microbial abundance (Bastida et al., 2008). In this study, RCO₂ values ranged from 1.90 to 9.47 μg CO₂ g⁻¹ h⁻¹, with no significant differences among treatments.

Microbial community is critical in nutrient cycling and overall soil health (Morugán-Coronado et al., 2022). The abundance of *Actinobacteria* was similar across all treatments, with no significant differences. However, the NPKA treatment exhibited the highest bacterial populations (both G⁻ and G⁺) as well as highest abundance of saprotrophic fungi, indicating favourable conditions for microbial proliferation. On the other hand, at T2, the MF treatment at 0–10 cm depth showed relatively lower populations of G⁻ bacteria and saprotrophic fungi.

3.4.3. Principal component analysis of microbial community

It can be observed from Fig. 3 that there was a strong positive correlation among soil microbial parameters in both soil layers (0–10 and 10–30 cm) during both sampling periods (T2 and T5). The strongest ($p < 0.001$) correlation were observed between G⁺ and G⁻ bacteria ($r = 0.85$), between both bacterial groups and *Actinobacteria* ($r = 0.97$ and $r = 0.94$, respectively). DHA showed significant positive correlations ($p < 0.001$) with MBC ($r = 0.46$), G⁺ ($r = 0.38$), G⁻ ($r = 0.55$),

Actinobacteria ($r = 0.49$) and saprotrophic fungi ($r = 0.77$). Similarly, MBC was significantly correlated ($p < 0.001$) with *Actinobacteria* ($r = 0.39$) and saprotrophic fungi ($r = 0.48$). At the same time, no significant correlations were found between basal respiration (RCO₂) and other microbial indicators.

A strong positive correlation ($p < 0.001$) was also observed between soil organic matter (OM%) and MBC ($r = 0.50$), and between DHA and pH_{KCl} ($r = 0.41$). Previous studies reported that soil pH is a key factor influencing microbial community composition and structure (Pietri and Brookes, 2009; Xia et al., 2020). Additionally, a positive correlation ($p < 0.05$) was found between DHA, MBC, saprotrophic fungi and total soil N ($r = 0.34$, $r = 0.26$ and $R = 0.20$, respectively). Liu et al. (2022) also emphasized the beneficial effects of moderate N inputs on microbial growth.

3.4.4. Soil fauna: springtails and mites

Microarthropods, such as mites and springtails, play an important role in accelerating the decomposition of organic matter and producing faecal pellets that enhance microbial activity (Betancur-Corredor et al., 2023). According to Tukey-Kramer test, the average abundances of springtails and mites showed no statistically significant differences between treatments (see Table 5). The abundance of springtails was significantly higher before fertilization (T1). After fertilization (T2), springtail numbers were low and relatively uniform across all treatments. After harvest (T5), abundance increased, with the highest — though not statistically significant — observed in the BP treatment (55.6 ± 10.7 individuals m² × 1000), which had a higher C/N ratio. Astigmata mites were not detected in any sample. The abundance of mites was also the highest at T1, particularly in the BP treatment (63.6 ± 10.1 individuals). At T2, the abundance of mites was the lowest in the FSP, PF and NPKA treatments (ranging from 8.7 to 10.3 individuals), while the highest value was found in the CON treatment (31.3 ± 8.8 individuals). At T5, mite populations had stabilized, with the highest abundance recorded in the NPKA treatment (44.6 ± 9.7 individuals).

Fig. 3. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of microbial community, DHA, MCB, RCO₂ and soil chemical properties in the 0–10 and 10–30 cm soil layers at T2 (one week after fertilization) and T5 (after harvest). Abbreviations: pH (KCl)- acidity of soil, OM- organic matter (%), SMN- soil mineral nitrogen (mg kg⁻¹), Total N- total nitrogen (g kg⁻¹), Total P- total phosphorus (g kg⁻¹), Mobile P- mobile phosphorus (g kg⁻¹), K- potassium (g kg⁻¹), S- sulphur (g kg⁻¹), Mg- magnesium (g kg⁻¹); Ca- calcium (g kg⁻¹); Na- sodium (g kg⁻¹), RCO₂(mg CO₂ g⁻¹ h⁻¹), MBC (ug C⁻¹g⁻¹ soil DM), DHA (μg g⁻¹ h⁻¹), soil moisture (%). Treatments: unfertilized (CON), mineral fertilizers (MF) and biobased fertilizers; bokashi pellet (BP), fish sludge pellet (FSP), protein fraction (PF) and NPK solution with amino acids (NPKA).

Table 5

Abundance of springtails and mites in the 0–20 cm soil layer at three sampling times: T1 (before fertilization), T2 (one week after fertilization), and T5 (after harvest), under different fertilizer treatments (mean ± SE, n = 12). S - number of species: individuals m⁻² (x1000); H - Shannon-Wiener diversity index.

Organisms	Treatment	T1	S	H	T2	S	H	T5	S	H
Springtails	CON	74.2 ± 22.8	14	1.668	20.5 ± 4.9	19	1.956	22.1 ± 4.5	14	1.778
	MF	108.1 ± 42.2	16	1.547	22.7 ± 5.0	14	1.858	22.3 ± 3.8	15	1.698
	BP	74.9 ± 25.2	18	1.665	24.5 ± 5.5	14	1.660	55.6 ± 10.7	18	1.846
	FSP	36.7 ± 7.7	17	1.595	23.9 ± 3.9	14	1.343	36.9 ± 5.6	13	1.920
	PF	59.2 ± 12.1	15	1.609	31.1 ± 12.9	10	1.489	40.8 ± 8.5	14	1.712
	NPKA	60.5 ± 13.9	18	1.666	21.6 ± 3.9	14	1.705	24.3 ± 3.1	12	1.536
Mites	CON	14.4 ± 3.5	-	-	16.0 ± 4.5	-	-	12.1 ± 1.5	-	-
	MF	25.1 ± 5.4	-	-	11.6 ± 1.5	-	-	19.1 ± 2.5	-	-
	BP	32.4 ± 5.1	-	-	10.3 ± 1.9	-	-	21.1 ± 1.8	-	-
	FSP	24.1 ± 2.5	-	-	5.3 ± 1.6	-	-	16.0 ± 2.6	-	-
	PF	21.5 ± 5.2	-	-	5.6 ± 1.3	-	-	16.1 ± 2.6	-	-
	NPKA	11.4 ± 1.8	-	-	4.4 ± 0.7	-	-	22.7 ± 4.9	-	-

Unfertilized (CON), mineral fertilizers (MF) and biobased fertilizers; bokashi pellet (BP), fish sludge pellet (FSP), protein fraction (PF) and NPK solution with amino acids (NPKA).

In total, 28 springtail species were identified throughout the experiment (species counts are given in Table 5). The highest number of species (19) was found in the CON treatment after the fertilization (T2), while the lowest (10) occurred in the PF treatment at the same time. The dominant species were *Protaphorura armata*, *Folsomia spinosa* and *Parisotoma notabilis*. The highest diversity index (1.956) was recorded in the CON plot at T2, while the lowest (1.343) was observed in the FSP plot at T2.

The application of both organic and inorganic N fertilizers to agricultural land can have mixed effects on soil fauna. While improved resource availability often benefits soil organism, negative effects may also arise due to the deterioration of soil physical-chemical properties (Betancur-Corredor et al., 2023). Although organic fertilizers generally enhance soil quality, support nutrient cycling, and promote microbial biomass formation, which increases the availability of food resources for soil fauna (Betancur-Corredor et al., 2023); in this experiment, the

abundance of soil organisms decreased following fertilization. The responses of soil fauna to fertilization are complex and may differ among organism groups due to the variations in their feeding habits (Betancur-Corredor et al., 2023). These responses likely result from multiple interacting factors, including fertilizer type, (organic vs. inorganic), application regimes, soil properties (e.g., pH, organic matter content, texture), and climatic factors.

3.4.5. Canonical correspondence analysis of springtails and mites

The CCA indicated that the primary differences in the composition of springtails and mites were related to the type of biobased fertilizer treatments. Soil data used in the CCA was obtained from the 0–30 cm soil layer. Additionally, the analysis assessed how soil data from the 0–10 cm and 10–30 cm layers influenced springtails and mites separately.

After the fertilization (T2), the main soil parameters were generally

positively correlated with each other (see Fig. 4). Plots treated with organic fertilizers (FSP, BP, PF) formed a distinct cluster, while those treated with NPKA, MF and CON clustered separately. Soil N content was positively correlated with soil P, S, and Ca content (R = 0.829 each). Similarly, soil S content was positively correlated with soil magnesium (Mg) (R = 0.829), Ca (R = 0.886), K (R = 0.829) and P content (R = 0.829).

Positive environmental effects were observed on soil organic matter (R = 0.812), N (R = 0.928) and P content (R = 0.841) for species *Pseudosinella alba* (Pse_alb), and species *Folsomia candida* (Fol_can) in relation to soil acidity (pH_{KCl}) (R=0.886). In contrast, *Stenaphorura denisi* (Ste_den) was negatively impacted by high levels of total N, total P, S, Mg, Ca, and K content (R = -0.828).

Comparing two soil depths, organic matter in the 0–10 cm layer influenced springtails both positively and negatively, whereas in the 10–30 cm layer, total P content had a more pronounced effect. Mites from the Prostigmata and Endeostigmata orders were influenced by environmental conditions. Specifically, Endeostigmata was positively affected by RCO₂ (R = 0.880) and negatively affected by soil organic matter (R = -0.880). Prostigmata order was negatively affected by soil total P and Ca content (R = -0.829). When analysing the effect of soil layer-specific data on mites, organic matter (R = -0.829), total N (R = -0.829), and total P (R = -0.886) from the 0–10 cm layer had the strongest negative impact on the Prostigmata order. From the 10–30 cm layer, soil moisture (R = -0.886), total P (R = -0.829), and Mg (R = -0.943) content had the greatest negative impact on the Oribatida

order.

After the harvesting (T5), several correlations emerged based on environmental conditions (see Fig. 5). Soil organic matter was negatively correlated with Mg (R = -0.943) and Na content (R = -0.829). Soil acidity (pH_{H2O}) showed a negative correlation with mobile P (R = -0.812), while soil moisture was negatively correlated with total P content (R = -0.943). S content was positively correlated with total P (R = 0.886) and total N content (R = 0.829).

Soil acidity (pH_{KCl}) had a greater positive impact on species *Folsomia candida* (Fol_can, R = 0.886), *Protaphorura armatus* (Pro_arm, R = 0.829), *Parisotoma notabilis* (Par_not, R = 0.886) and *Isotomiella minor* (Iso_min, R = 0.812). *Sphaeridia pumilis* (Sph_pum) was positively influenced by soil total P (R = 0.886), total N content (R = 0.829) and S content (R = 0.829), whereas *Paratullbergia callipygos* (Par_cal), showed negative correlations with the same parameters (R = -0.886 and R = -0.829, respectively).

When examining soil depth, microbial biomass carbon (MBC) and dehydrogenase activity (DHA) had a strong positive influence on several springtail species, especially in the 0–10 cm layer. Specifically, MBC positively affected *Protaphorura armatus* (Pro_arm, R = 0.886); *Folsomia candida* (Fol_can, R = 0.829); *Parisotoma notabilis* (Par_not, R = 0.829); *Isotomiella minor* (Iso_min, R = 0.928)). DHA had positive effects on *Folsomia candida* (Fol_can, R = 0.886); *Parisotoma notabilis* (Par_not, R = 0.886); *Pseudosinella alba* (Pse_alb, R = 0.829) and *Isotomiella minor* (Iso_min, R = 0.986)).

In autumn, soil mites were generally less influenced by environmental conditions. However, soil acidity (pH_{H2O}) had a positive affect on the Mesostigmata order (R = 0.812), RCO₂ positively influenced the Endeostigmata order (R = 0.812), and soil K content negatively affected the Prostigmata order (R = -0.829).

Fig. 4. Ordination triplots with environmental variables based on Canonical Correspondence Analyses (CCA) of species at T2 (one week after fertilization). Abbreviations: pH (H₂O)- acidity of soil, pH (KCl)- acidity of soil, OM- organic matter (%), Total N- total nitrogen (g/kg), Total P- total phosphorus (g/kg), Mobile P- mobile phosphorus (g/kg), K- potassium (g/kg), S- sulphur (g/kg), Mg- magnesium (g/kg); Ca- calcium (g/kg); Na- sodium (g/kg), RCO₂(mg CO₂/g/h), MBC (ug C/g soil d.w), DHA (μg/g/h), soil moisture (%). Eigenvalues of the first two axes are 51.7 % and 27.1 %; the sum of all canonical eigenvalues is 0.236. Treatments: unfertilized (CON), mineral fertilizers (MF) and biobased fertilizers; bokashi pellet (BP), fish sludge pellet (FSP), protein fraction (PF) and NPK solution with amino acids (NPKA).

Fig. 5. Ordination triplots with environmental variables based on Canonical Correspondence Analyses (CCA) of species at T5 (after harvest). Abbreviations: pH (H₂O)- acidity of soil, pH (KCl)- acidity of soil, OM- organic matter (%), Total N- total nitrogen (g/kg), Total P- total phosphorus (g/kg), Mobile P- mobile phosphorus (g/kg), K- potassium (g/kg), S- sulphur (g/kg), Mg- magnesium (g/kg); Ca- calcium (g/kg); Na- sodium (g/kg), RCO₂(mg CO₂/g/h), MBC (ug C/g soil d.w), DHA (μg/g/h), soil moisture (%). Eigenvalues of the first two axes are 50.7 % and 35.1 %; the sum of all canonical eigenvalues is 0.231. Treatments: unfertilized (CON), mineral fertilizers (MF) and biobased fertilizers; bokashi pellet (BP), fish sludge pellet (FSP), protein fraction (PF) and NPK solution with amino acids (NPKA).

When soil indicators were analyzed by depth, parameters from the 0–10 cm layer had a stronger positive effect on mites. The Prostigmata order was positively influenced by MBC ($R = 0.886$) and DHA ($R = 0.829$). The Endeostigmata order responded positively to mobile P ($R = 0.928$) and Mg ($R = 0.812$), while the Oribatida order was negatively affected by Na content ($R = -0.886$). Soil parameters from the 10–30 cm layer had a less pronounced influence on mites. Na content negatively affected the Mesostigmata order ($R = -0.886$), and K content negatively affected the Oribatida order ($R = -0.829$).

According to Gisin (1943), organisms can be classified into various life-form groups based on their physical traits, which are indicative of their physiological and ecological characteristics. These groups include: (1) Epiedaphic organisms, which inhabit the soil surface and the litter layer. (2) Euedaphic organisms, which are found within the soil profile, and (3) Hemiedaphic organisms, which display intermediate morphological, physiological, and ecological traits between the epiedaphic and euedaphic forms (Lavelle and Spain, 2005; Lux et al., 2024). As shown in Table 6, the ecological groups of euedaphic and hemiedaphic springtails (%) were more prominently represented at all sampling times. In contrast, the proportion of epiedaphic springtails (%) was initially low before the experiment began, but showed a slight increase as the experiment progressed.

The abundance of springtails can significantly influence soil function and the delivery of ecosystem services. Faecal pellets produced by springtails, primarily from hemi and euedaphic species, may constitute a significant portion of organic matter and essential nutrients, thereby enhancing soil fertility and promoting plant growth. In addition to improving soil and plant characteristics, springtails also affect nutrient distribution within the soil, affecting plant functional traits such as root architecture. Some studies suggest that high densities of euedaphic springtails in the rhizosphere can lead to reduced root growth. This response is attributed to increased nutrient availability, prompting plants to reallocate energy from root development to aboveground traits such as biomass accumulation, flowering time, and seed production. (Bellini et al., 2023). This trend likely results from the feeding activity and localized excreta deposition of euedaphic springtails near plant roots.

The biobased fertilizers tested — particularly pelleted formulations such as BP and FSP — demonstrated potential to enhance soil microbial activity, as indicated by elevated levels of MBC and DHA. Although changes in soil chemical properties were generally modest and short-lived, shifts in microbial functioning were more pronounced. These treatments also subtly influenced soil faunal communities, notably promoting the abundance of certain springtail taxa under bokashi treatment. However, overall species richness and diversity tended to decline following fertilization. Soil mesofauna responses were closely linked to changes in pH, C/N ratio, and microbial activity, highlighting the complexity of belowground interactions. These findings suggest that organic fertilizers can shape soil biological functioning beyond mere nutrient input, reinforcing their relevance in sustainable soil management strategies.

Table 6

Proportion of ecological groups of springtails (%) in the 0–20 cm soil layer at three sampling times: T1 (before fertilization), T2 (one week after fertilization), and T5 (after harvest), under different fertilizer treatments ($n = 4$). E-epiedaphic, EU-euedaphic, HE-hemiedaphic.

Treatment	Depth, cm	E	T1 EU	HE	E	T2 EU	HE	E	T5 EU	HE
CON	0–20	0.9	52.1	46.9	8.9	40.5	50.6	2.7	59.0	38.3
MF	0–20	0.6	41.2	58.2	3.4	55.6	41.0	4.2	42.7	53.1
BP	0–20	2.5	39.9	57.7	2.3	62.4	35.4	0.9	69.1	30.0
FSP	0–20	2.8	43.4	53.9	1.6	68.4	30.0	3.1	63.5	33.4
PF	0–20	2.3	32.0	65.7	0.3	69.8	30.0	3.1	57.2	39.7
NPKA	0–20	1.6	37.3	61.1	11.0	55.7	33.3	5.4	41.3	53.3

Unfertilized (CON), mineral fertilizers (MF) and biobased fertilizers; bokashi pellet (BP), fish sludge pellet (FSP), protein fraction (PF) and NPK solution with amino acids (NPKA).

3.5. Nitrate residues after harvesting

Nitrate residues from N inputs and plant residues remaining after harvest can lead to leaching, posing threat to groundwater bodies. The Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) requires EU member states to identify nitrate-vulnerable zones (NVZs) and implement action programs that limit fertilizer use in order to reduce nitrate leaching into water bodies. Although the study site was not located within designated NVZs in Estonia, the fertilization rate was determined in accordance with the Nitrates Directive and crop nutrient requirements. This approach aimed to avoid excessive N application and minimize the risk of nitrate leaching into the environment.

Broccoli roots are primarily concentrated in the topsoil (0–15 cm) (Wyland et al., 1996); however, Smith et al. (2016) reported that broccoli roots can extend to depths of approximately 1 m by harvest, with around 70 % located within the top 40 cm and about 90 % within the top 60 cm of the soil profile. Due to the crop's high N demand, SMN levels of the treatments decreased drastically across the treatments (see Fig. 6), falling below 40 kg ha^{-1} , with most of the remaining N present as $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$. At T1 (before fertilization), the $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ content in the 0–60 cm soil layer was $103 \pm 33 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$. By T4 (harvest time), residual $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ levels had declined below 28 kg ha^{-1} across all treatments. A slight increase in soil nitrate content was observed post-harvest (T5), but levels remained under 34 kg ha^{-1} in all treatments.

Substantial N mineralization from broccoli residues typically occurs within 2–3 months (Smith et al., 2016). In November 2023 (T6 – monitoring of residual nitrate), nitrate levels in the 0–60 cm soil profile rose to $42\text{--}66 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ across treatments, remaining significantly lower than the pre-fertilization levels at T1. Soil nitrate from plant residues and unused fertilizers was monitored at this stage to assess potential environmental impacts.

Nitrogen surplus — calculated as the difference between fertilizer N input and crop N uptake — is a widely used indicator for estimating nitrate leaching risk (Huang et al., 2017). The same study highlighted that a low or negative N surplus is associated with reduced nitrate leaching. In our study, crop N uptake ranged from 165 to 315 kg N ha^{-1} for fertilized treatments and 152 kg N ha^{-1} for the CON, while the fertilization rate was 120 kg N ha^{-1} . These values indicate a negative N surplus, suggesting minimal to no nitrate leaching rate by harvest. Moreover, winter wheat with potential long root system can further reduce N leaching risks (Huang et al., 2017; Thorup-Kristensen et al., 2009). Based on these findings, the applied fertilization rate of 120 kg N ha^{-1} for broccoli cultivation is unlikely to result in nitrate residue levels that would pose a contamination risk to groundwater in the study area.

3.6. Opportunities and challenges towards sustainable agriculture and healthy soils

Promoting soil health and sustainable agricultural practices through organic fertilization presents both opportunities and challenges. The use of biobased fertilizers can enhance soil fertility, and in many cases, perform comparably to synthetic mineral fertilizers in supporting plant

Fig. 6. Soil nitrate residues in the 0–60 cm soil layer at T5 (after harvest) and T6 (monitoring of residual nitrate). Unfertilized (CON), mineral fertilizers (MF) and biobased fertilizers; bokashi pellet (BP), fish sludge pellet (FSP), protein fraction (PF) and NPK solution with amino acids (NPKA).

growth and crop yield. Additionally, organic fertilizers enriched with primary and secondary macronutrients, as well as micronutrients, can contribute to improved soil health.

In this study, the tested biobased fertilizers — derived from fishery waste and/or by-products — exhibited beneficial effects on microbial communities, whereas the application of MF was associated with reduced soil microbial activity. A rich and abundant microbial community supports the mineralization of nutrient-rich organic amendments. Over the longer term, soils treated with organic fertilizers often show increased populations of soil mesofauna. In our experiment, the abundance of springtails and mites initially declined after fertilization but showed a slight recovery post-harvest.

To optimize crop yield and N uptake, the C/N ratio of organic biobased fertilizers should be considered. In the BP treatment, a strong microbial response — indicated by high DHA and MBC — led to net N immobilization during the early growth stages, which inhibited crop development. Although the BP product, produced via composting, contains a relatively high amount of N, its elevated C/N ratio and slow N release make it more suitable as a long-term soil improver rather than a short-term fertilizer.

In contrast, both the liquid NPKA and the solid PF showed no significant differences from MF in terms of broccoli head yield and NUE, indicating strong potential for these products to serve as effective alternatives to synthetic N fertilizers. The fish sludge derived solid (FSP) also demonstrated promise as a partial replacement for its synthetic counterpart.

The use of fishery waste-derived fertilizers in agriculture helps minimize waste generation, promotes nutrient recycling, reduces reliance on synthetic mineral fertilizers. However, due to the variability in nutrient content and release rates of organic fertilizers, farmers may need to adjust their management practices to achieve optimal crop yields and minimize nutrient losses.

On the policy side, existing regulations regarding the use of organic fertilizers — particularly in arable and organic farming systems — may discourage farmers from adopting biobased alternatives. Animal by-products, such as fish waste, continue to raise safety concerns among policymakers, which can further hinder their widespread acceptance. To overcome these challenges, support from both stakeholders and policymakers is essential. Ensuring the availability and quality of certified biobased fertilizers, while addressing regulatory and resource constraints, will be critical for advancing soil health and sustainable agriculture within the framework of circular economy.

4. Conclusions

The results of this study provides novel field-scale evidence on the agronomic, environmental and ecological performance of various fishery waste-derived fertilizers. It integrates biological soil health metrics with crop productivity and nitrogen (N) dynamics to evaluate both functional and environmental outcomes. Notably, this research moves beyond the greenhouse and pot-based experiments predominant in existing literature, offering a more comprehensive understanding of biobased fertilizer performance under practical field conditions.

Biobased fertilizers derived from fishery waste and by-products — specifically the liquid nutrient solution with amino acids (NPKA) and the loose solid protein fraction (PF) — exhibited N release dynamics patterns and early-stage soil mineral nitrogen (SMN) availability comparable to mineral fertilizer (MF). Their application resulted in similar broccoli biomass yield and N use efficiency, supporting their potential as effective alternatives to synthetic fertilizers in temperate agroecosystems. The fish sludge pellet product (FSP), with intermediate mineralization rates, may serve as a partial replacement when fertilization timing and dosage are optimized.

The study confirmed that early SMN levels at 0–30 cm and 0–60 cm soil depths are reliable indicators of subsequent N uptake and crop yield. When applied at a rate of 120 kg N ha⁻¹ following red clover incorporation, treatments with these fertilizers achieved high crop productivity while maintaining a low risk of N leaching, demonstrating effective nutrient synchrony with crop demand.

Short-term application of these biobased fertilizers did not significantly alter soil physical-chemical parameters but noticeably enhanced microbial activity. These changes suggest a stimulatory effect on soil microbial functioning, particularly from fertilizers derived from fishery waste and by-products. However, the abundance of springtails and mites generally declined, possibly due to soil disturbance or changes in nutrient dynamics, indicating the need for further investigation over longer timeframes.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Merili Toom: Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Marta Aranguren:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Birgit Koll:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Irene Roman:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Stefaan De Neve:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Jingsi Zhang:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Erik Meers:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Susana Virgel Mentxaka: Formal analysis, Data curation. **Anneli Kuu:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Çağrı Akyol:** Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Liina Edesi:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Tiina Talve:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.still.2025.106686](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2025.106686).

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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